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Numerical modeling, analysis, and simulations for the space-time wave equation with velocity initial and final time conditions

David Jean Baptiste Bilong (david.bilong@aims-cameroon.org)
African Institute for Mathematical Sciences (AIMS)
Cameroon

Supervised by: Prof.Dr. Thomas Wick
Leibniz University Hannover, Germany

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Abstract

Two variations of the wave equation are examined in this paper with typical beginning circumstances, the first one match the classical wave equation. The second is a recently suggested space-time variational material model where mechanical, thermal, and internal factors interact. It is derived from a thermodynamically consistent Hamilton functional defined across a space time domain. The apparition of a non-standard final time velocity condition in the second order wave equation is a characteristic of this model. We extract and evaluate the wave equation independently, ignoring temperature and internal variables, in order to better grasp the ramifications of the unusual boundary conditions in time. We perform then a Galerkin finite element discretization in time and space for both problem cases. Moreover, we investigate the behavior of these formulations using numerical simulations based on the discretization.

Key words: Final time velocity condition, Galerkin finite element discretization, Variational material model, Space-time, Wave equation.

Declaration

I, the undersigned, hereby declare that the work contained in this essay is my original work, and that any work done by others or by myself previously has been acknowledged and referenced accordingly.

DAVID JEAN BAPTISTE BILONG, 28 May 2025.

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1. Introduction

Over years physicists have been interested by studying complex phenomena implying different variables and this ended sometime with system of equations specifically partial differential equations (PDEs) with derivatives showing the high order of the model, and due to the difficulty for the most of them to be directly solve, numerical methods have then been introduced by mathematicians to try to find an approximate solution having an error approximation as smaller as possible.

More specifically in modelisation of complex phenomena implying applied mechanics and thermodynamics and when dealing with elastic body we lead to the so-called elastic wave equation which is a system of non linear PDEs of second order in displacement variable called usually " u " depending of the space and time with boundaries and initial conditions, the latest usually initial displacement and velocity conditions prescribed to have a well-posed problem.

However by analyzing that system of equation more closely, we can remark the imposition of conditions almost everywhere except to the top cover of the space-time cylinder, "cylinder" here is a word use in the field to specify the domain where we work in and having a spatial and temporal dimension. Recently in [11] scientists wishing to study a case of having conditions on the full entire system to see the influence on that on the solution, have got a new variational formulation deriving by using a well construct extended Hamilton functional, and a famous principle from Hamilton, the Hamilton principle, saw the first time in 1836 in his book [8], this is going to expose us at an unusual initial velocity conditions replacing the usual initial displacement condition, a new formulation which is actually part of a whole thermo-mechanical coupled problem implying the reduce set of thermodynamical states $\{\theta, u\}$, where θ is the temperature variable [11].

A first numerical study has been made on that unusual system of wave equation in [12] to study the influence of that new condition by using the so-called Galerkin Finite element method more specifically the continuous one use in time and space which allows as finite element method for more flexibility in the discretization.

In this thesis, we aim to add at the first investigation, some new insights by using the same numerical space-time approach (continuous Galerkin finite element method) and more numerical implementations and give some differences raised by doing a comparative study, an exploration on the differences of the error approximations of our results between the classical sense (with usual initial conditions and the new formulation with final time condition added) to get out the important parameters influencing the error approximations in order to understand the influence of our newly conditions.

1.1 Problem Statement

This work focuses on the study of our new wave equation system with an unusual final time condition on the velocity. First, we aim to study the approximate solution first of the classical wave equation using the continuous Galerkin finite element method in space and time and also by being interested to the order of the error in order to do a comparison later. Secondly, we will study also the approximate solution and the order of the error for our system with our unusual initial condition. Then, by conducting a comparative analysis on the error approximation, we will compare the approximate solutions coming from the two different posed problems in order to understand and get more insights on the influence of our new condition.

By analyzing the simulation results, we try to understand the numerical behavior on the error approximations from the different cases. Moreover, we will extract and study the behavior of the important parameters influencing our understanding and give us more insights on how the error changes with the change of parameters numerically in the two cases.

1.2 Literature Review

Variational calculus which is the notion used in order to describe physically observed phenomena, specifically coming from applied mechanics have evolved during the years. Many works in that field have been done into the aim trying to describe by variational calculus and energy principles as more as possible the physical phenomena or even exactly how it behaves. Among the methods developed based on energy variations on a body, we have the so-called Hamilton's principle developed for the first time by Hamilton [8] in 1834 which has given the key to get in some cases the so-called weak variational formulation without going through the strong one with strong imposition of boundary conditions.

From that period, with the time the principle has evolved and scientists has started to understand so many other things, specifically the possibility to impose weakly conditions on a model by adding some terms in the Hamilton functional before applying the Hamilton's principle rather to impose strong conditions on the system. In this regard, a recent work has been done by Philipp Junker and Daniel Balzani [10]. They have showed how to derive evolution equations with state variables by using the Hamilton's principle and give an example on the use of the extended Hamilton's principle to derive evolution equations in thermo-elastic materials for small deformations.

An interesting direct application of that idea has been the key to construct the extended Hamilton functional, constructed by Thomas Wick and Philipp Junker [11], getting at the end of derivations an unusual final time condition [11].

To study such kind of system of elastic wave equation in space time of second order, we need numerical methods as finite element methods in space and finite difference one in time, this method works but sometime depending of the order of the error with which we want to get at the end, the so-called Galerkin finite element method gives more advantages in the flexibility within the discretization and then on the error. Work on the advantages by theoretical and rigorous proofs have been done in [9] by T.J.R. Hughes and G.M. Hulbert in order to support the idea for using Galerkin finite element method specifically discontinuous there, for this kind of problem (elastic wave equation) and more generally for hyperbolic equations of second order.

More specifically for our case a work which has been very useful to understand and have the order of convergence of the continuous Galerkin finite element method applied on the so-called elastic wave equation in the classical sense with usual initial conditions has been developed in [3, 7]. So far the study made by all those different scientists from applied mechanics and mathematics for the study of evolution equations described by PDEs and suitable numerical methods as Galerkin finite element method to approximate solutions have played a fundamental role on our understanding of physical phenomena as displacement of particles in an elastic body case.

1.3 Thesis Organization

This thesis investigates the numerical modeling and analysis of the classical and unusual wave equations, focusing on the impact of final time velocity condition using the continuous finite element Galerkin method (cG-FEM). The thesis begins with an introduction in Chapter 1, outlining the problem, reviewing relevant literature, and defining the objectives. In Chapter 2, we present the mathematical formulations of both wave equations, by detailing the classical elasto-dynamics model and deriving the unusual model via thermodynamic principles and an extended Hamiltonian approach. After that Chapter 3 follows describing the cG-FEM discretization for both cases, including fully discrete variational problems. Finally, Chapter 4 presents numerical simulations conducted on FEniCS, including some analysis, key findings, limitations and future research directions.

2. Elastic wave equations: Two perspectives

2.1 Classical linear elasto dynamics problem

2.1.1 Preliminaries. Here, we consider an open bounded region $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$, with d the dimension of the space which can take as value 1,2 or 3. We call $\partial\Omega$ the boundary of Ω and which is supposed smooth so that we can define an outward normal vector n on it.

Furthermore, we assume to have the boundary which can be decomposed as $\partial\Omega = \overline{\partial\Omega_N} \cup \overline{\partial\Omega_D}$ with $\partial\Omega_N$ and $\partial\Omega_D$ are two disjoint sets meaning that $\partial\Omega_N \cap \partial\Omega_D = \emptyset$. Here, $\partial\Omega_N$ is in fact where we impose the boundary Newman condition to the system, and $\partial\Omega_D$ is the one where the Dirichlet condition is imposed. This is the definition of the spatial space. We also consider the interval of time $I = [0, T]$ with $T \in]0, +\infty[$, T here is the time length interval of the time domain T .

2.1.2 Problem's Model. Here, we assume to have an elastic body occupying the region Ω not necessarily consider homogeneous in which we applied a force f in the body's volume such that $f : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ and a traction forces on the surface's boundary of Ω (specifically $\partial\Omega_N$) $g_N : \partial\Omega_N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ and a prescribe boundary displacement condition on Dirichlet boundary describe by the function $g_D : \partial\Omega_D \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$. Also we consider the vector displacement $u(x, t)$ depending on space and time describing the evolution of the wave created by the action of the forces in our body.

Due to the external forces applied on the body, we have a deformation(strain) of the body and there is a constraint force created by the body to resist to the deformation, the so-called stress which is denoted by σ and depend of ∇u and is given by the Hooke's law which gives the proportional relation between the deformation(strain) and the stress, by the formula:

$$\sigma(\nabla u) = c \cdot \epsilon(u),$$

where:

- c is the dilatational wave velocity which changes depending of the material and its nature. For example for the isotropic case(where the properties of the material are the same in all the direction) c is given by $c = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda+2\mu}{\rho}}$, λ and μ are called Lamé parameters, depend of the body and ρ the density of the body ;(see more in [9]).

It's also worth mentioning even though it will not be helpful for us in our developments, that c is actually a fourth order tensor which respect some symmetry properties as: $c_{ijkl} = c_{jikl} = c_{ijlk} = c_{klij}$ properties that is very helpful to analyze a numerical solution of the wave equation system below by using numerical method as discontinuous Galerkin finite element(see more in [9]).

- the strain(deformation) represented by ϵ is given by the formula:

$$\epsilon(u) = \frac{1}{2}(\nabla u + \nabla^t u).$$

Under the assumption of small displacements, we have the displacement variable u which respect the following system:

$$\begin{cases} \rho \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} - \nabla \cdot \sigma(\nabla u) = f, & \text{on } \Omega \times]0, T[\\ u = g_D, & \text{on } \partial\Omega_D \times]0, T[\\ n \cdot \sigma(\nabla(u)) = g_N, & \text{on } \partial\Omega_N \times]0, T[\\ u(x, 0) = u_0(x), & x \in \Omega \\ \dot{u}(x, 0) = v_0(x), & x \in \Omega. \end{cases} \quad (2.1.1)$$

Here, we have the imposition of the two initials conditions to ensure the well-posedness of the problem (i.e., existence, uniqueness of the solution and its continuously depending of the data) since we have a partial differential equation of second order in time.

2.1.3 Example with $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}$. We have in this case σ which can be written as $\sigma = cu'$ with $c > 0$, u' is the spatial derivative and \dot{u} the temporal one. The system which can then still be written in this case as follow

$$\begin{cases} \rho \ddot{u} - cu'' = f, & \text{on } \Omega \times]0, T[\\ u = g_D, & \text{on } \partial\Omega_D \times]0, T[\\ cu' = g_N, & \text{on } \partial\Omega_N \times]0, T[\\ u(x, 0) = u_0(x), & x \in \Omega \\ \dot{u}(x, 0) = v_0(x), & x \in \Omega. \end{cases} \quad (2.1.2)$$

2.2 Wave equation problem from elastodynamic with final time velocity conditions

2.2.1 Motivation. As we can see previously in the Section 2.1 where we get out the usual model of the elastic wave equation, we raised that the boundary conditions and initial conditions are imposed on the following parts: $\partial\Omega_D \times]0, T[$, $\partial\Omega_N \times]0, T[$, $\Omega \times \{0\}$, so in fact our conditions cover almost all the system except the top cover of the cylinder. So, a main motivation of this study specifically of this part is to capture the entire surface, define conditions on the entire surface and this is going to lead us at our new perspective of our system with a new condition on time. A derivation of such system has been introduced and demonstrated by Philipp Junker and Thomas Wick [11].

Note. In the following parts we will consider the same preliminaries as in the Section 2.1 .

2.2.2 Thermodynamical states. Considering our bounded region Ω and an elastic body included inside, in each spatial point x we define or there are properties related to our body, we have two types of material properties: time-dependent material property and time-independent one. In fact time-independent properties are linked to constant parameters , but here we will be interested on those which are time-dependent usually called Thermodynamic state variables which basically in the thermodynamic is the set having the displacement u , temperature θ , and the internal variables related to the material α for example it can be the concentration, the plastic strain, the damage state or a combination of them(details can be found in [10]), but for our study of the wave equation for an elastic body we will restrict our study with the thermodynamical state variables which are the displacement and the temperature. $S := \{u, \theta\}$.

2.2.3 Remark. Again as recall, our word cylinder that we use here is just an another name to mean our body inside a spatial-time domain. Indeed we can see our spatial domain Ω as a circle through which a temporal dimension passes creating the so-called space-time cylinder.

2.2.4 Useful laws from thermodynamic. Our final goal on this part will be to give a description of the evolution of thermodynamic state variables with the inclusion of our new condition, but first of all, we have to give some important laws that we need, to be able to conduct a good derivation. More details on these laws can be found in [2, 10].

- **First law of thermodynamic**

This is the law so-called balance of energy and states that the balance of energy which states the rate of the total energy of the body equals the power due to the mechanical and thermal loads and is translated by the following relation:

$$\dot{\mathcal{E}} + \dot{\mathcal{K}} = \mathcal{P}^{mech} + \mathcal{P}^{therm}. \quad (2.2.1)$$

Then, by integrating this equation by time we obtain the equivalence equation below with energies with some constant but we set the constant null and work with it without harming the generality (see more details in [10]).

$$\mathcal{K} + \mathcal{E} = \mathcal{W} + \mathcal{Q}. \quad (2.2.2)$$

Integrating equation 2.2.2 over time again, we have the following results

$$\int_I \mathcal{K} dt + \int_I \mathcal{E} dt = \int_I \mathcal{W} dt + \int_I \mathcal{Q} dt, \quad (2.2.3)$$

with:

- The **kinetic** energy \mathcal{K} is given by: $\mathcal{K}(u) = \int_{\Omega} \frac{1}{2} \rho \|u\|^2 dV$
- The **internal** energy \mathcal{E} is given by: $\mathcal{E}[u, \theta] = \int_{\Omega} \psi(\epsilon, \theta) dV + \int_{\Omega} \theta s dV$.

2.2.5 Remark. Generally \mathcal{E} depends also of α but for our case we have considered no internal variables.

- the **external mechanical** work \mathcal{W} given by the expression: $\mathcal{W}(u) = \int_{\Omega} f \cdot u dV + \int_{\partial\Omega_N} g_N \cdot u dA$.
- **external thermal** work \mathcal{Q} given by: $\mathcal{Q} = \int_{\Omega} \int h dt dV - \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,\theta}} \int n \cdot q dt dA$

where

- ρ is the density of the body with unit kg/m^3 .
- ψ with unit J/m^3 is the free energy density, s is the entropy density with unit $[s] = J/km^3$.
- The heat flux on the surface q with unit W/m^2 , the body force f with unit N/m^3 , the external heat source h with unit W/m^3 , and the traction force g_N with unit N/m^2 are the quantities given and threaten as constants.
- We have ϵ which is as in the Section 2.1 the strain or deformation dimensionless and $\sigma = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \epsilon}$ with unit of σ which is N/m^2 .
- $q = -w \nabla(\theta)$, with w which is the heat conductivity and $[w] = W/mK$

2.2.6 Remark. We can remark the lack of boundaries in the integral over time of the expression of the external thermal work, but in $\int h dt$ has to be understood in fact as the quantities of the heat arriving over time at a certain point of Ω and $\int n \cdot q dt$ also has to be understood just as the heat flux over time on the boundary.

• **Second law of thermodynamic**

The second law so-called balance of entropy state that: Having two bodies of difference temperatures, their difference in temperature will be compensated by lowering the temperature of the body which initially had higher body temperature and increasing the temperature of the one which had initially lower temperature.

In fact the measure of the degree of repartition and exchanges of the heat in the different systems is what we call the entropy. We denote here:

- The **total** entropy by S .
- The entropy **flux** which is the way with which the heat moves into the system denote by Q_f^s .
- The entropy **source** which is what cause the increase of the entropy created inside the system Q_s^s .
- The entropy **production** \mathcal{D} which is a measure of the irreversibility of the heat exchanges and the internal transformations, so for the irreversible processes(case where the temperature goes from systems of high temperature to low's ones) we have: $\mathcal{D} \geq 0$.

The second is translated by the formula's expression:

$$\dot{S} = Q_s^s + Q_f^s + \mathcal{D}, \quad (2.2.4)$$

with:

- The total entropy $S = \int_{\Omega} s dV$,
- The entropy source $Q_s^s = \int_{\Omega} \frac{h}{\theta} dV$,
- the flux entropy $Q_f^s = - \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,\theta}} n \cdot \frac{q}{\theta} dA$,
- The production entropy $\mathcal{D} = \int_{\Omega} \Delta^s dV$.

• **Important Definitions** (see in [11])

First let us define the **free energy** denoted by g and depending of (u, θ) is given by:

$$g[u, \theta] := \int_{\Omega} \psi(\epsilon, \theta) dV.$$

Secondly, let us also define the **total potential** g_I given by:

$$g_I := \int_I g dt - \int_I \int_{\Omega} f \cdot u dV dt - \int_I \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,u}} g_N \cdot u dA dt. \quad (2.2.5)$$

Also, let us define what we call an **action** and **total action**.

An action is the evolution of thermodynamical state variables specifically in each material point and is given then by integration over the set of the points (in the cylinder) of the value dA which

is the elementary action and it's the integration of the value \dot{u} over the curve with fixed start $u(0)$ and end point $u(T)$ taken by the specific point where dm is the elementary mass since the position over the curve is entirely related to the displacement variable.

So, we have:

$$d\mathcal{A} = \int_u dm \cdot \dot{u} du, \quad \text{or} \quad dm = \rho dV \quad \text{so,}$$

$$d\mathcal{A} = \int_u \rho \dot{u} \cdot du dV \quad \text{also} \quad du = \dot{u} dt \quad \text{so,}$$

Integrating the above equation, we have that

$$\mathcal{A} = \int_{\Omega} d\mathcal{A} = \int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho \|\dot{u}\|^2 dV dt.$$

where \mathcal{A} here is the so-called action.

Now we can define the total action which comes from the idea that having fixed the start and end point the displacement variable is not really interesting for us at those points so we can remove them and finally define the total action \mathcal{A}_I as:

$$\mathcal{A}_I = \mathcal{A} - \int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u}^* \cdot u dV ds, \quad (2.2.6)$$

with $\partial I = \{0, T\}$.

2.2.7 Proposition. An important equality which will be helpful for us is the next steps, which comes from the combination of the first and second law of the thermodynamic, is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_I \mathcal{K} dt &= - \int_I g dt + \int_I \int_{\Omega} f \cdot u dV dt + \int_I \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,u}} g_N \cdot u dA dt - \int_I \int_{\Omega} \int \dot{\theta} s dt dV dt \\ &\quad - \int_I \int_{\Omega} \int \frac{1}{\theta} q \cdot \nabla \theta dt dV dt - \int_I \int_{\Omega} \int \Delta^s \theta dt dV dt. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. The proof to this proposition is inspired by the research published in [10].

From the first law of the thermodynamic, we have

$$\int_I \mathcal{K} dt + \int_I \mathcal{E} dt = \int_I \mathcal{W} dt + \int_I \mathcal{Q} dt, \quad (2.2.7)$$

which can still be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \int_I \left(\int_{\Omega} \frac{1}{2} \rho \|\dot{u}\|^2 dV + \int_{\Omega} (\psi + \theta s) dV \right) dt &= \int_I \left(\int_{\Omega} f \cdot u dV + \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,u}} g_N \cdot u dA \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \int_{\Omega} \int h dt dV - \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,\theta}} \int n \cdot q dt dA \right) dt \end{aligned}$$

From an another hand, considering the second law we have

$$\dot{S} = \mathcal{Q}_s^s + \mathcal{Q}_f^s + \mathcal{D},$$

which can still be written as

$$\dot{S} = \int_{\Omega} \frac{h}{\theta} dV - \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,\theta}} n \cdot \frac{q}{\theta} dA + \int_{\Omega} \Delta^s dV.$$

Looking for h , we get

$$\int_{\Omega} \frac{h}{\theta} dV = \int_{\Omega} \dot{s} dV + \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,\theta}} n \cdot \frac{q}{\theta} dA - \int_{\Omega} \Delta^s dV.$$

By multiplying the last line by θ inside of the integrals, we get

$$\int_{\Omega} \frac{h}{\theta} \cdot \theta dV = \int_{\Omega} \theta \dot{s} dV + \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,\theta}} n \cdot \frac{q}{\theta} \cdot \theta dA - \int_{\Omega} \theta \Delta^s dV,$$

and we then get:

$$\int_{\Omega} h dV = \int_{\Omega} \theta \dot{s} dV + \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,\theta}} n \cdot q dA - \int_{\Omega} \theta \Delta^s dV.$$

By substituting the last equation into the expression of the thermal work \mathcal{Q} , we get that

$$\mathcal{Q} = \int_{\Omega} \int h dt dV - \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,\theta}} \int n \cdot q dt dA = \int_{\Omega} \int \theta \dot{s} dt dV - \int_{\Omega} \int \theta \Delta^s dt dV.$$

Moreover, we can easily remark that

$$\int_I \int_{\Omega} \int \theta \dot{s} dt dV dt + \int_I \int_{\Omega} \int \dot{\theta} s dt dV dt = \int_I \int_{\Omega} \theta s dV dt.$$

So, we obtain from the first law's expression just above and replacing the equation

$$\begin{aligned} \int_I \mathcal{K} dt &= - \int_I g dt + \int_I \int_{\Omega} f \cdot u dV dt + \int_I \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,u}} g_N \cdot u dA dt - \int_I \int_{\Omega} \int \dot{\theta} s dt dV dt \\ &\quad - \int_I \int_{\Omega} \int \Delta^s \theta dt dV dt. \end{aligned} \tag{2.2.8}$$

Now, the entropy production term include the contribution from all the dissipative processes and then has to include a term which is not negligible and is the so-called heat flux term due to the heat conduction which is denoted by $\Delta_{heat}^s \theta$ where:

$$\Delta_{heat}^s = -\frac{q}{\theta^2} \cdot \nabla \theta.$$

We can also see from the Fourier's law $q = -w \cdot \nabla \theta$ that:

$$\Delta_{heat}^s = -\frac{q}{\theta^2} \cdot \nabla \theta = w \frac{\|\nabla \theta\|^2}{\theta^2} \geq 0.$$

So, we can see that $\Delta_{heat}^s \geq 0$ respect the condition of the second law of the thermodynamic as it enters in the entropy production's expression.

So, we should then add to our equation 2.2.8 the term

$$\int_I \int_{\Omega} \int \Delta_{heat}^s \cdot \theta dt dV dt.$$

So, finally we get the equation

$$\begin{aligned} \int_I \mathcal{K} dt &= - \int_I g dt + \int_I \int_{\Omega} f \cdot u dV dt + \int_I \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,u}} g_N \cdot u dA dt - \int_I \int_{\Omega} \int \dot{\theta} s dt dV dt \\ &\quad - \int_I \int_{\Omega} \int \frac{1}{\theta} q \cdot \nabla \theta dt dV dt - \int_I \int_{\Omega} \int \Delta^s \theta dt dV dt. \end{aligned}$$

□

2.2.8 Important principles. The goal of this section is to define a functional which by deriving it using some fundamental principles, we lead to a variational formulation of the elastodynamic wave equations including a new unusual condition, we will study some classical case of those principles before to comeback to our case.

- **Classical principle of least action**

This is a principle which gives a variational approach in order to describe the evolution of a particle in a dynamical system, it's explain by the statement that the momentum integrated along the path that a rigid particle follows tend to be stationary (see in [10]) just to mean that the path taken by a particle is the one which tend to extremize the functional.

We can write it as:

$$\delta \mathcal{A} = \delta \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \mathcal{L}(\dot{v}, v, t) dt = 0,$$

where:

- Here \mathcal{A} is the action.
- Here \mathcal{L} is usually the difference of energy, called again functional (more details below)
- Here δ is the variation and v the variable.

Note. More details on the following example can be found in [11]

2.2.9 Example. ([11])

Here we give a small idea of what we are going to do in the next parts.

If we consider the functional \mathcal{L} define by:

$$\mathcal{L} := \int_I \left(\frac{1}{2} m \dot{v}^2 - \frac{1}{2} k v^2 \right) dt,$$

where v depends of t , m the mass and the positive spring constant k , using the stationary condition we get

$$\delta \mathcal{L} = 0 \implies \delta \int_I \left(\frac{1}{2} m \dot{v}^2 - \frac{1}{2} k v^2 \right) dt = 0$$

So we get

$$\begin{aligned}\delta\mathcal{L} &= \int_I (m\dot{v}\delta\dot{v} - kv\delta v) dt \quad \forall \delta v \\ &= m\dot{v}\delta v|_{t=T} - m\dot{v}\delta v|_{t=0} - \int_I (m\ddot{v} + kv)\delta v dt = 0, \quad \forall \delta v\end{aligned}$$

We have done the integration by part to have the last equality. To have the equality null, since terms are independent each other we need them to vanish one by one, so it's necessary to have:

- $m\ddot{v} + kv = 0$ is the ordinary differential equation (ODE) of second order traducing the dynamic of an harmonic oscillator. To solve this kind of ODE we need two conditions on the variable v and its first derivative in initial and or final time which is usually prescribed.
- Also we can remark here that the function δv has to vanish at the initial time and end time. But we do not use that assumption usually, because actually we do not need to have or we do not want to have conditions on the functions δv since we are studying and seeking the path which tend to the extrema our functional from a more global sense, so imposing conditions on the functions δv can lead us to a problem not well posed.

• Principle of virtual work including initial conditions

Here the goal using the same idea as previously, is to deal with an extended functional from where the derivative is going to give us the usual elastodynamic wave model with initial/boundary conditions coming from a weak form by stationary condition. More details on what we develop here can be found in [11].

But first of all let us define our functional \mathcal{L} .

Let set the functional as:

$$\mathcal{L} = \int_I K - g_I dt - \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u}_0^* \cdot u dV|_{t=0} + \frac{1}{2} c_u \|u - u_0^*\|^2 dV|_{t=0}.$$

- The term $\int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u}_0^* \cdot u dV|_{t=0}$ ensure that the weak form that we are going to have is influenced by the initial velocity condition prescribed \dot{u}_0^* , so it serves to enforce weakly this condition.
- the term $\frac{1}{2} c_u \|u - u_0^*\|^2 dV|_{t=0}$ is the penalization term and it is here to ensure that the solution in initial time is near of the initial solution displacement prescribe u_0^* and the more higher is c_u the more we can enforce the solution to be close of the one prescribe in initial time u_0^* , see more details in [10, 11].

By using the stationary condition $\delta_u \mathcal{L} = 0$, we get:

$$\begin{aligned}\delta_u \mathcal{L} &= \int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u} \cdot \delta u dV dt - \int_I \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \epsilon} : \delta \epsilon dV dt + \int_I \int_{\Omega} f \cdot \delta u dV dt \\ &\quad + \int_I \int_{\partial \Omega_N, u} g_N \cdot \delta u dA dt - \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u}_0^* \cdot \delta u dV|_{t=0} + \int_{\Omega} c_u (u - u_0^*) \cdot \delta u dV|_{t=0} = 0, \quad \forall \delta u.\end{aligned}$$

By integration by part and taking in consideration that $\sigma = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \epsilon}$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \delta_u \mathcal{L} = & \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u} \cdot \delta u dV|_{t=T} - \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u} \cdot \delta u dV|_{t=0} - \int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho \ddot{u} \cdot \delta u dV dt \\
 & + \int_I \int_{\Omega} \nabla \cdot \sigma \cdot \delta u dV dt - \int_I \int_{\Omega} \nabla \cdot (\sigma \cdot \delta u) dV dt + \int_I \int_{\Omega} f \cdot \delta u dV dt \\
 & + \int_I \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,u}} g_N \cdot \delta u dAdt - \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u}_0^* \cdot \delta u dV|_{t=0} + \int_{\Omega} c_u (u - u_0^*) \cdot \delta u dV|_{t=0} = 0, \quad \forall \delta u.
 \end{aligned}$$

By now using Gauss's theorem that we recall by the formula with integration in time

$$\int_I \int_{\Omega} \nabla \cdot (\sigma \cdot \delta u) dV dt = \int_I \int_{\partial\Omega} n \cdot \sigma \cdot \delta u dAdt.$$

We get then:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \delta_u \mathcal{L} = & \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u} \cdot \delta u dV|_{t=T} - \int_I \int_{\Omega} (\rho \ddot{u} - \nabla \cdot \sigma - f) \cdot \delta u dV dt - \int_{\Omega} \rho (\dot{u} - \dot{u}_0^*) \cdot \delta u dV|_{t=0} \\
 & - \int_I \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,u}} (n \cdot \sigma - g_N) \cdot \delta u dAdt + \int_{\Omega} c_u (u - u_0^*) \cdot \delta u dV|_{t=0} = 0, \quad \forall \delta u.
 \end{aligned}$$

For this equality to vanish, since those integrals are account independently regarding to the volume or surface where they are defined, we must ask that each of these values must vanish and we will get:

- The equation expressing of the second law of newton which is:

$$\rho \ddot{u} - \nabla \cdot \sigma - f = 0 \text{ on } \Omega \times I.$$

- The Newman boundary condition which is: $n \cdot \sigma = g_N$ on $\partial\Omega_{N,u}$
- The prescribed velocity at the initial time (\dot{u}_0^*) is equal to the velocity in initial time: $\dot{u}(0) = \dot{u}_0^*$
- The same for the displacement u which is successfully equal to the prescribed one in initial time.
- But again the bad news is the constraint on the function δu which must vanish in end time, what we cannot accept, since again we would like to work without restricted constraints for the functions δu because first it could cause a ill-posed problem(over-constraints) but moreover we would like to work as more generally without restricting the set of admissible path of our problem of finding the path which tend the functional to be extreme.

2.2.10 Remark. To solve the last problem raised, we will see that by imposition a final condition, we will have the opportunity to remove our constraint over the set of test functions (name that we are going to use from now for functions denoted by $\delta \mathbf{u}$). Moreover, also we do not forget our motivation to add a condition on the top cover of our space time cylinder which will be solved at the same time.

2.2.11 Modeling of our system with unusual final time condition. A recent study for the construction of this system has been done by Philipp Junker and Thomas Wick [11]. Our goal here will be to derive the system once more using the same idea than we have got in the previous example but here by not using the principle of least action particularly but its generalization, the so-called, Hamilton principle, more details and explanations on it can be found in [10].

- **Construction of the extended Hamilton functional** : Here, our goal is to build a functional to which we are going to apply the Hamilton principle that we are going to see below again. In order to derive a weak formulation of our propositional case with final time condition.

So, to do that a very careful construction has been chosen (see more details in [11]) in order to apply the Hamilton principle which is described as follows.

We consider our definition again on total action, equation 2.2.6 which can again be define as:

$$A_I := 2\mathcal{K} - \int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u}^* \cdot u dV ds.$$

On the other hand, by using the equality given in Proposition 2.2.7 coming actually from the two fundamental laws of thermodynamic, we can then replace in A_I one of the two \mathcal{K} by this equality from Proposition 2.2.7. The part containing the expression of A_I without the value $\int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u}^* \cdot u dV ds$ will be called the **principal** part of our functional.

The word **extended** will come from the other terms which in fact for a mathematical purpose are additional terms containing all our conditions that we wish to impose weakly and then of course the value $-\int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u}^* \cdot u dV ds$ will enter in those additional terms.

The additional terms are defined in what we denote here \mathcal{H}^{Ad} defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{H}^{Ad}[u, \theta] := & \int_I \int_{\partial\Omega_{D,u}} \frac{1}{2} c_u \|u - g_D\|^2 dAdt - \int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u}^* \cdot u dV ds \\ & + \int_I \int_{\partial\Omega_{D,\theta}} \frac{1}{2} c_\theta (\theta - \theta^*)^2 dAdt + \int_{\Omega} \frac{1}{2} k (\theta - \theta_0^*)^2 dV|_{t=0}. \end{aligned}$$

- At $t = 0$ the expression $\int_{\Omega} \frac{1}{2} k (\theta - \theta_0^*)^2 dV|_{t=0}$ is use to impose the initial temperature θ_0^*
- The term $\int_I \int_{\partial\Omega_{D,u}} \frac{1}{2} c_u \|u - g_D\|^2 dAdt$ is used to impose the term of the boundary Dirichlet condition on the displacement and the same for the similar term for temperature.
- The term $-\int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u}^* \cdot u dV ds$ is used to impose the initial and end time velocity condition to the system which is our goal, with $\partial I = \{0, T\}$
- c_u, c_θ are such that: $[c_u] = Kg/m^3 s, [c_\theta] = Kg/msK^2$.
- The heat capacity is denoted by k , with $[k] = J/m^3 k$

Finally, we can define the extended Hamilton functional that we denote by H^{Ex} here:

$$H^{Ex}[u, \theta] = H_{pr}[u, \theta] + \mathcal{H}^{Ad}[u, \theta].$$

The term $H_{pr}[u, \theta]$ is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} H_{pr}[u, \theta] = & \int_I (\mathcal{K} - g_I - \int_{\Omega} \int \dot{\theta} s dt dV \\ & - \int_{\Omega} \int \frac{1}{\theta} q \cdot \nabla \theta dt dV - \int_{\Omega} \int \Delta^s \theta dt dV) dt. \end{aligned}$$

Note. It worth mentioning to recall that g_I is our equation 3.2.5 defining the total potential.

- **Utilisation of the Hamilton principle** : The Hamilton principle is used here from a similar way to what we have seen before with the principle of the least action. Indeed the both in the modern literature are the same and almost used from the same way, but it is worth mentioning

that historically the principle of least action was dealing with an action with more restriction where the time was not consider as an independent variable ,the Hamilton principle is more general and have with objective to derive the Lagrange equations for the dynamical systems, see more in [8].

So, again using the stationary condition from the Hamiltonian principle as in the principle of least action shown above, we get:

$$\delta H[u, \theta](\delta u, \delta \theta) = 0 \quad \forall \delta u, \delta \theta. \quad (2.2.9)$$

Before to continuing to the details, let us see the following proposition.

2.2.12 Proposition. [11, 6]

Let $\mathcal{F}: \Omega \subset X \rightarrow Y$ be a mapping with $X = X_1 \times X_2$, here $u \in X_1$ and $\theta \in X_2$, and X, Y are normed vector spaces and Ω open set. If \mathcal{F} is differentiable at a point $a \in \Omega$, the N ($N=2$ here due to u, θ) partial derivatives $(\partial_j \mathcal{F}(a)(\delta a_j))_{1 \leq j \leq N}$ exist and it holds into all directions $\delta a(\delta a_1, \dots, \delta a_N) \in X$ that:

$$\mathcal{F}'[a](\delta a) = \sum_{j=1}^N \partial_j \mathcal{F}(a)(\delta a_j).$$

Proof. see [6], Theorem 7.1-2, p.455 □

So, using the Proposition 2.2.12, we can still write equation 2.2.9 as:

$$\delta H[u, \theta](\delta u, \delta \theta) = \delta_u H[u, \theta](\delta u) + \delta_\theta H[u, \theta](\delta \theta) = 0 \quad \forall \delta u, \delta \theta.$$

2.2.13 Definition. [11]

Let X and Y be normed vector spaces again and Ω and open set in X . Here we suppose $Y = \mathbb{R}$, and we consider $\mathcal{G}: \Omega \subset X \rightarrow Y$ be a mapping, $b \in \Omega$ and a non zero vector $\delta b \in X$. Let assume the parameter $\epsilon \in \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathcal{G}(b + \epsilon \delta b) \in Y$ is differentiable at $\epsilon = 0$. Then, \mathcal{G} has at $b \in \Omega$ the gâteaux derivative into the direction δb , meaning in fact a directional derivative which is defined by

$$\delta \mathcal{G}[b](\delta b) := \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{\mathcal{G}(b + \epsilon \delta b) - \mathcal{G}(b)}{\epsilon}, \quad \text{with } \delta \mathcal{G}[b](\delta b) \in Y.$$

2.2.14 Proposition. Using the definition above, we get the gateaux derivatives of H below which vanish each one because in the equation just above the variables are independent so to get that equality, we need each gâteaux derivative to vanish. More specifically when $\delta_u H[u, \theta](\delta u) = 0$, we get

$$\begin{cases} \int_I \left(\int_\Omega \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \epsilon} : \delta \epsilon dV - \int_\Omega f \cdot \delta u dV - \int_{\partial \Omega_{N,u}} g_N \cdot \delta u dA \right) dt - \int_I \int_\Omega \rho \dot{u} \cdot \delta \dot{u} dV dt \\ - \int_I \int_{\partial \Omega_{D,u}} c_u(u - g_D) \cdot \delta u dA dt + \int_{\partial I} \int_\Omega \rho \dot{u}^* \cdot \delta u dV ds = 0, \quad \forall \delta u. \end{cases}$$

Proof. Let us show that :

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_u H[u, \theta](\delta u) &= \int_I \left(\int_\Omega \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \epsilon} : \delta \epsilon dV - \int_\Omega f \cdot \delta u dV - \int_{\partial \Omega_{N,u}} g_N \cdot \delta u dA \right) dt - \int_I \int_\Omega \rho \dot{u} \cdot \delta \dot{u} dV dt \\ &\quad - \int_I \int_{\partial \Omega_{D,u}} c_u(u - g_D) \cdot \delta u dA dt + \int_{\partial I} \int_\Omega \rho \dot{u}^* \cdot \delta u dV ds = 0, \quad \forall \delta u. \end{aligned}$$

We have :

$$H^{Ex}[u, \theta] = H_{pr}[u, \theta] + \mathcal{H}^{Ad}[u, \theta]$$

Let us focus on the principal part H_{pr} and derive its terms one by one, we have:

$$\delta_u \mathcal{K} = \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u} \cdot \delta \dot{u}, \quad \text{so} \quad \delta_u \int_I \mathcal{K} dt = \int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u} \cdot \delta \dot{u} dV dt.$$

Moreover,

$$g_I = \int_{\Omega} \psi(\epsilon, \theta) dV - \int_{\Omega} \rho \cdot u dV - \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,u}} g_N \cdot u dA,$$

where ϵ depends on u as in the following expression:

$$\epsilon = \frac{1}{2}(\nabla u + \nabla^T u), \quad \delta \epsilon = \frac{1}{2}(\nabla \delta u + \nabla^T \delta u).$$

So,

$$\delta_u g_I = \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \epsilon} : \delta \epsilon dV - \int_{\Omega} f \cdot \delta u dV - \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,u}} g_N \cdot \delta u dA.$$

We can remark that all the other terms (thermal ones) do not depend of the variable u so at the end we get:

$$\delta_u H_{Pr} = \int_I \left(\int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u} \cdot \delta \dot{u} dV - \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \epsilon} : \delta \epsilon dV + \int_{\Omega} f \cdot \delta u dV + \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,u}} g_N \cdot \delta u dA \right) dt.$$

For the additional terms included in H^{Ad} , by deriving them we get:

$$\delta_u H^{Ad} = \int_I \int_{\partial\Omega_{D,u}} c_u \cdot (u - g_D) \cdot \delta u dA dt - \int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u}^* \cdot \delta u dV dt.$$

Finally, we get the equality:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_u H[u, \theta](\delta u) &= \int_I \left(\int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \epsilon} : \delta \epsilon dV - \int_{\Omega} f \cdot \delta u dV - \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,u}} g_N \cdot \delta u dA \right) dt - \int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u} \cdot \delta \dot{u} dV dt \\ &\quad - \int_I \int_{\partial\Omega_{D,u}} c_u (u - g_D) \cdot \delta u dA dt + \int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u}^* \cdot \delta u dV ds = 0 \quad \forall \delta u = 0. \end{aligned}$$

□

2.2.15 Remark. We have in this equation the direction δu which are admissible directions in a suitable function space. The system is also known as the so-called weak form of the balance of linear momentum for the displacement vector u .

Differently from the usual formulation or classical one we have even though it is weakly imposed the initial and final time condition on the velocity.

Also this equality from the previous Proposition 2.2.14 can still be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & - \int_{\Omega} \rho(\dot{u} - \dot{u}_T^*) \cdot \delta \dot{u} dV|_{t=T} + \int_{\Omega} (\rho \ddot{u} - \nabla \cdot \sigma - f) \cdot \delta u dV dt - \int_{\Omega} \rho(\dot{u} - \dot{u}_0^*) \cdot \delta u dV|_{t=0} \\
 & + \int_I \int_{\partial \Omega_{N,u}} (n \cdot \sigma - g_N) \cdot \delta u dAdt + \int_I \int_{\partial \Omega_{D,u}} c_u(u - g_D) \cdot \delta u dAdt = 0, \quad \forall \delta u.
 \end{aligned}$$

Since using the Cauchy's law we have that

$$\int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \epsilon} : \delta \epsilon dV = \int_{\Omega} \nabla \cdot (\sigma \cdot \delta u) dV - \int_{\Omega} \nabla \cdot \sigma \cdot \delta u dV = \int_{\partial \Omega_{N,u}} n \cdot \sigma \cdot \delta u dAdt - \int_{\Omega} \nabla \cdot \sigma \cdot \delta u dV.$$

And by integration by parts, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 - \int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u} \cdot \delta \dot{u} dV dt + \int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u}^* \cdot \delta u dV ds &= - \int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho(\dot{u} - \dot{u}^*) \cdot \delta u dV ds + \int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho \ddot{u} \cdot \delta u dV dt \\
 &= - \int_{\Omega} \rho(\dot{u} - \dot{u}^*) \cdot \delta u dV|_{t=T} - \int_{\Omega} \rho(\dot{u} - \dot{u}^*) \cdot \delta u dV|_{t=0} \\
 &+ \int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho \ddot{u} \cdot \delta u dV dt.
 \end{aligned}$$

2.2.16 Remark. So the equation above is the weak variational formulation of our wave elastic system of equation with initial and final time condition. By using the fact that the equality has to be vanished and each of those values are independent regarding to the domain of integration, each one of them has to vanish and we get the system that we call strong formulation given by:

$$\begin{cases} \rho \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} - \nabla \cdot \sigma(\nabla u) = f, & \text{on } \Omega \times]0, T[\\ u = g_D, & \text{on } \partial \Omega_D \times]0, T[\\ n \cdot \sigma(\nabla(u)) = g_N, & \text{on } \partial \Omega_N \times]0, T[\\ \dot{u}(x, T) = \dot{u}_T^*(x), & x \in \Omega \\ \dot{u}(x, 0) = \dot{u}_0^*(x), & x \in \Omega \end{cases} \quad (2.2.10)$$

3. Space-time Galerkin finite element method applied to both models.

In this chapter, we first give some mathematical preliminaries as spaces that we deal with to define the discrete spaces necessary for our Continuous Galerkin discretization. Secondly, we applied the space-time Continuous Galerkin method for the classical wave equation. Finally, we applied for our unusual wave equation system with initial and final time velocity conditions.

3.1 Mathematical preliminaries

Here, we give some definitions of the L^2 space, Sobolev space (more specifically $H^1(\Omega)$), also we define what we call by Dual space, we define the euclidean norm in \mathbb{R}^d and the so-called time-dependent Sobolev space assuming to have a space $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$ which is an open bounded region with a sufficient regular boundary.

3.1.1 L^2 spaces(see in [5]). This space L^2 is the one of all the measurable functions $u : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ (or \mathbb{C}) that are square-integrable with respect to the Lebesgue measure define as,

$$L^2(\Omega) = \{u : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \mid \int_{\Omega} |u(x)|^2 dx < \infty\}.$$

This space is equipped with the inner product,

$$(u, v)_{L^2} = \int_{\Omega} u(x)v(x)dx,$$

which induces the norm given as

$$\|u\|_{L^2} = \left(\int_{\Omega} \|u(x)\|^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}.$$

3.1.2 Sobolev's space H^1 (see in [5]). The Sobolev space H^1 consists of functions in L^2 whose the first derivative are also in L^2 and define on Ω by:

$$H^1(\Omega) = \{u \in L^2(\Omega) \mid \nabla u \in L^2(\Omega)\}.$$

3.1.3 Dual space(see in [5]). Let V be an Hilbert space(e.g. $V=L^2(\Omega)$, $H^1(\Omega)$) with the norm $\|\cdot\|_V$, we call the Dual space of V denoted by V^* the set of all continuous linear functionals on V . And if we consider a linear functional f in V^* and $v \in V$ we define in fact the duality pairing between them by:

$$\langle f, v \rangle_{V^*, V} = f(v).$$

For example, we can consider $V=L^2(\Omega)$, the set $V^* = L^2(\Omega)$ and the pairing is

$$\langle f, v \rangle_{L^2, L^2} = \int_{\Omega} f(x)v(x)dx.$$

3.1.4 Time-dependent Sobolev space(see in [5]). We consider our time interval $I = [0, T]$ and V an Hilbert space with norm $\|\cdot\|_V$; We define the time-dependent Sobolev space $L^2(I, V)$ which consists of all measurable functions $u: I \rightarrow V$ such that

$$\int_I \|u(t)\|_V^2 dt < \infty.$$

The inducing norm is given by the expression

$$\|u(t)\|_{L^2(I, V)}^2 = \left(\int_I \|u(t)\|_V^2 dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}.$$

3.1.5 Euclidean norm in \mathbb{R}^d (see in [5]). We define the euclidean norm in \mathbb{R}^d denoted here as $\|\cdot\|$ by

$$\forall x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_d), \quad \|u\| = \left(\sum_{i=1}^d x_i^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}.$$

3.2 Continuous Galerkin method applied to the classical linear elastodynamic model

Here, we consider the following system which is the strong formulation of the wave equation of elastodynamic (see in the Subsection 2.1) but we set $\dot{u} = v$, this is for an objective of numerical order.

So, we have the following system

$$\begin{cases} \rho \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} - \nabla \cdot \sigma(\nabla u) = f, & \text{on } \Omega \times]0, T[\\ \dot{u} = v, & \text{on } \Omega \times]0, T[\\ u = g_D, & \text{on } \partial\Omega_D \times]0, T[\\ n \cdot \sigma(\nabla(u)) = g_N, & \text{on } \partial\Omega_N \times]0, T[\\ u(x, 0) = u_0(x), & x \in \Omega \\ v(x, 0) = v_0(x), & x \in \Omega \end{cases} \quad (3.2.1)$$

In fact, the setting of $\dot{u} = v$ allows us to discretize the system with the idea to have two different quantities of solutions which are u and v .

3.2.1 Function Spaces. Here, we define the spaces that we need in order to make a good discretization of our above system.

- **Displacement vector**

Since we have a non homogeneous boundary condition of Dirichlet, what we first define here is:

$$\mathcal{W}_0^u := \{u \in H^1(\Omega)^d \mid u = 0 \text{ on } \partial\Omega_D\}.$$

This is the set of function of H^1 but vanish on the Dirichlet boundary of Ω .

Note. Here, the "0" just means that we consider the homogeneous Dirichlet boundary condition, that is u vanishing on that Dirichlet boundary. \mathcal{W}_0^u serves us as **spatial** test function spaces that we name in our work as displacement variation δu . The word spatial since we have not yet

taken in consideration the temporal dimension, we will see down the final set taking in account the regularity of the test function in time.

Now, we have to define our spatial space also within the "u" solution displacement is going to live in space. To do that, we consider the space

$$\mathcal{W}^u = \{g_D + \mathcal{W}_0^u\}.$$

This is the spatial space of our solution, that we call here trial spatial space.

We can clearly remark that in space, we have the test functions which are living in a different space from the trial functions due to the non homogeneous Dirichlet conditions. An importance of that is generally on the establishment of the variational formulation (see in [4], Chapter 2 for more details).

Now, considering the L^2 regularity necessary in time of the solution, we define the sets:

$$u \in \mathcal{H}^u = L^2(I, W) \text{ and } \delta u \in \mathcal{H}_0^u = L^2(I, W_0^u).$$

- **Velocity vector**

Concerning the velocity v , it worth mentioning that we have no spatial boundary conditions on v , and this means that we are not going as in the case of the displacement vector consider the space for test functions different from the one of the trial functions spatially.

So, let consider the space $W^v = L^2(\Omega)^d$, this is the spatial space for the test function or velocity variations denoted here by δv and also for the trial functions v and as done in the previous part and considering the regularity in time of the velocity, we define the space:

$$\mathcal{H}^v := L^2(I, W^v).$$

After defining this set we can now claim our final goal in the next parts which will be to find a solution of our weak formulation that we will give down in the following specific sets and solutions, $u \in \mathcal{H}^u$, $v \in \mathcal{H}^v$ and $\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} \in L^2(I, (W^u)^*)$.

We have $(W^u)^*$ is the dual space associated to W^u , and the latter partial derivative is taken in this set.

3.2.2 Weak Formulation. We define the weak formulation and give a proof of it, this is an expression deriving from the strong formulation above and expressed in the function spaces that we have defined just above.

The definition of this weak formulation is relevant for the discretization scheme, the key of our interest for the following parts.

3.2.3 Proposition. The weak formulation associated to the strong formulation is given by finding $u \in \mathcal{H}^u, v \in \mathcal{H}^v$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho \partial_t v \cdot \delta u dV dt + \int_I \int_{\Omega} \sigma(\nabla u) : \nabla \delta u dV dt + \int_I \int_{\Omega} (\partial_t u - v) \cdot \delta v dV dt \\ = \int_I \int_{\Omega} f \cdot \delta u dV dt + \int_I \int_{\partial\Omega_N} g_N \cdot \delta u dA dt, \end{aligned}$$

with $\forall \delta u \in \mathcal{H}_0^u$, $\delta v \in \mathcal{H}_v$ and initial conditions $u(x, 0) = u_0$ and $v(x, 0) = v_0$ in Ω , $f: \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$, $g_N: \partial\Omega_N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$.

Proof. We consider the system in equation 3.2.1 above which is the strong formulation of the classical system of elastodynamic wave equation. By multiplying by δu , the first line and by δv the equation $\dot{u} = v$, the test functions, and integrating simultaneously over $\Omega \times I$ we get: $\forall \delta u \in \mathcal{H}_0^u, \delta v \in \mathcal{H}_v$:

$$\int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho \partial_t v \cdot \delta u dV dt - \int_I \int_{\Omega} (\nabla \cdot \sigma) \cdot \delta u dV dt = \int_I \int_{\Omega} f \cdot \delta u dV dt, \quad (3.2.2)$$

$$\int_I \int_{\Omega} (\partial_t u - v) \cdot \delta v dV dt = 0.$$

But let's remark that by integrating by parts over space the integral of $(\nabla \cdot \sigma) \cdot \delta u$, we get:

$$\int_{\Omega} (\nabla \cdot \sigma) \cdot \delta u dV = - \int_{\Omega} \sigma : \nabla \delta u dV + \int_{\partial \Omega_N} (\sigma \cdot n) \cdot \delta u dV. \quad (3.2.3)$$

Normally, we should also have a term over the Dirichlet boundary but since the test function $\delta u (\delta u \in \mathcal{H}_0^u)$ vanishes over the Dirichlet boundary ($\partial \Omega_D$), we have the integral over the Dirichlet boundary which does not appear on the above expression.

So, by replacing the equation 3.2.3 in the equation 3.2.2, we get:

$$\int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho \partial_t v \cdot \delta u dV dt + \int_I \int_{\Omega} \sigma : \nabla \delta u dV dt = \int_I \int_{\partial \Omega_N} g_N \cdot \delta u dA dt + \int_I \int_{\Omega} f \cdot \delta u dV dt, \quad (3.2.4)$$

$$\int_I \int_{\Omega} (\partial_t u - v) \cdot \delta v dV dt = 0.$$

Finally, by addition of the two latest equations, we get the weak formulation:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho \partial_t v \cdot \delta u dV dt + \int_I \int_{\Omega} \sigma(\nabla u) : \nabla \delta u dV dt + \int_I \int_{\Omega} (\partial_t u - v) \cdot \delta v dV dt \\ = \int_I \int_{\Omega} f \cdot \delta u dV dt + \int_I \int_{\partial \Omega_N} g_N \cdot \delta u dA dt, \end{aligned}$$

with $u(x, 0) = u_0(x)$ and $v(x, 0) = v_0(x)$.

□

3.2.4 Continuous Galerkin Discretization. Our goal here is to describe mathematically the continuous Galerkin discretization of this classical case. To do that we are going to define a finite dimensional set in space in which we are going to project our problem in space and then use the continuous Galerkin finite element method in time to fully discretize our problem in space time.

Also the opposite can be done starting by defining a temporal discrete space in which we can project our problem and then fully discretize in space but for implementation it is usually done by the first method to easily implement. More details can be found on the paper [3].

- **Spatial Finite Dimensional Element Space**

We consider a decomposition of the set $\bar{\Omega}$ into non overlapping elements K which can be triangle elements in dimension 2 or tetrahedra elements in dimension 3 for example.

We call by h_k the local mesh size given by the formula: $h_k = \text{diam}(K) = \sup_{x,y \in K} \|x - y\|$ and we define $h := \max_{K \in T_h}$, where we set $T_h = \{K\}_{K \in \Omega}$, a decomposition into non-overlapping elements of $\bar{\Omega}$.

Let us define $W_h \subset W^u$ be a finite dimensional space containing the polynomials of degree less than or equal to s where:

$$W_h = \{u_h \in C(\bar{\Omega})^d \mid (u_h)|_K \in \mathbb{P}_s(K)^d, \forall K \in T_h\}. \quad (3.2.5)$$

As we will see later it's in this set that we will approximate the solution $u_h(t)$ and $v_h(t) \forall t \in I$ in space, this discrete set contains a local basis of polynomial which can be Lagrange polynomial of degree at most s . In this method of Galerkin the displacement test functions are also taken in this space.

- **Temporal discretization**

We have our temporal interval which is I , lets decompose our interval I into M non overlapping subintervals such that $I = \bigcup_{m=1}^M$, where:

$$I_m = [t_{m-1}, t_m], \quad k_m = t_m - t_{m-1}, \quad k := \max_{m \in \{1, \dots, M\}} k_m.$$

- In each subinterval we use a polynomial of degree r for the approximation of the solution which is assume continue in time.
- But for the approximation of test functions we assume to use polynomial of degree $r - 1$ since the test functions in the continuous Galerkin method are assumed globally discontinuous in time.

Indeed due to the globally continuity of the trial functions we have the trial functions which by the obligation to linked subintervals by continuity is going to fixed a value at t_m for each subinterval which is going to make us lost one degree of freedom by that condition in t_m so to have a system well-posed we just need test functions of order $r - 1$ in each subinterval. More details can be found in [3].

Lets recall our weak formulation by now adding the initial conditions imposed to the system in the weak formulation but we should pay attention on how adding them.

Lets take in consideration the weak formulation which is equivalent to the one in Proposition (3.2.3):

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{m=1}^M \int_{I_m} \int_{\Omega} \rho \partial_t v \cdot \delta u dV dt + \sum_{m=1}^M \int_{I_m} \int_{\Omega} \sigma : \nabla \delta u dV dt + \int_{\Omega} \rho v(x, 0) \cdot \delta v dV \\ & = \int_{\Omega} \rho v_0 \cdot \delta v dV + \sum_{m=1}^M \int_{I_m} \int_{\partial \Omega_N} g_N \cdot \delta u dA dt + \sum_{m=1}^M \int_{I_m} \int_{\Omega} f \cdot \delta u dV dt, \\ & \sum_{m=1}^M \int_{I_m} \int_{\Omega} (\dot{u} - v) \cdot \delta v dV dt + \int_{\Omega} \rho u(x, 0) \cdot \delta u dV = + \int_{\Omega} \rho u_0 \cdot \delta u dV. \end{aligned}$$

Note. We can remark like we said up the additions of the initials conditions, specifically the initial displacement has been added in two equations from 3.2.4 but here discretized, just because they represent respectively initial conditions on u for the first degree differential equation in u and the initial condition on the velocity for the same reason on the first equation.

- **Temporal Finite Element Space :** We are going to define some important spaces to discretize in time our weak formulation given above.

- * First of all for the trial functions, we define the set as

$$W_{h,k}^c := \{u \in C^0(\bar{I}, W_h) \mid u|_{I_m} \in \mathbb{P}_r(I_m, W_h), \forall m = 1, 2, \dots, M\}. \quad (3.2.6)$$

This is the set where leave the trial functions which are the functions solutions in space time. The parameter c is just to mean globally continuous functions.

- * We also define the set of test functions by:

$$W_{h,k}^d := \{u \in L^2(\bar{I}, W_h) \mid u|_{I_m} \in \mathbb{P}_{r-1}(I_m, W_h), \forall m = 1, 2, \dots, M\}. \quad (3.2.7)$$

Here, we need the L^2 regularity of the test function looking at our variational formulation. This is where live the discontinuous (the reason of the "d") function tests (discontinuous in t_m).

3.2.5 Remark. We can remark here our use of the set W_h which is not unusual, this traduce the space-time discetization in the continuous Galerkin method.

- **Fully Discrete Variational Formulation**

Finally, we can define the fully discrete variational formulation by the space time continuous Galerkin method as $\forall(\delta u, \delta v) \in W_{h,k}^d \times W_{h,k}^d$. Then, we seek to find the couple solution $(u, v) \in W_{h,k}^c \times W_{h,k}^c$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{m=1}^M \int_{I_m} \int_{\Omega} \rho \partial_t v \cdot \delta u dV dt + \sum_{m=1}^M \int_{I_m} \int_{\Omega} \sigma : \nabla \delta u dV dt + \int_{\Omega} \rho v(x, 0) \cdot \delta v dV \\ & = \int_{\Omega} \rho v_0 \cdot \delta v dV + \sum_{m=1}^M \int_{I_m} \int_{\partial\Omega_N} g_N \cdot \delta u dA dt + \sum_{m=1}^M \int_{I_m} \int_{\Omega} f \cdot \delta u dV dt, \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.8)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^M \int_{I_m} \int_{\Omega} (\partial_t u - v) \cdot \delta v dV dt + \int_{\Omega} \rho u(x, 0) \cdot \delta u dV = \int_{\Omega} \rho u_0 \cdot \delta u dV.$$

3.3 Continous Galerkin method applied to our unusual model

In this section, we first define the function spaces to perform a good discretization.

3.3.1 Function spaces. Similar to the previous section, we define the function spaces necessary to well define our weak formulation.

We recall:

$$\mathcal{W}_0^u := \{u \in H^1(\Omega)^d \mid u = 0 \text{ on } \partial\Omega_D\} \text{ and } \mathcal{W}^u = \{g_D + \mathcal{W}_0^u\}.$$

Again, here nothing has changed the displacement variable u live spatially within the space \mathcal{W}^u and the displacement variation δu spatially within \mathcal{W}_0^u due to the non homogeneous Dirichlet boundary condition.

Also, we define the space $\mathcal{W}^v = L^2(\Omega)^d$ the spatial space where live the test and trial functions of velocity. Now in space-time by considering the L^2 regularity in time of the of u and v we get also we give the same notations again as in the previous section:

- The trial function displacements $u \in \mathcal{H}^u := L^2(I, W^u)$.
- The displacement variation $\delta u \in \mathcal{H}_0^u := L^2(I, W_0^u)$.
- The trial velocity $v, \delta v \in \mathcal{H}^v := L^2(I, W^v)$.
- The partial derivative of the velocity $\partial_t v \in L^2(I, (W^v)^*)$.

3.3.2 Weak Formulation. The weak formulation has been derived in Chapter 2 and we recall it here and write it in the space-time sets defined above.

3.3.3 Proposition. The weak formulation of our case is given by the expression $\forall \delta u \in \mathcal{H}_0^u$ and $\forall \delta v \in \mathcal{H}^v$:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_I \int_{\Omega} \sigma : \nabla \delta u dV + \int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{v} \cdot \delta u dV dt - \int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho v \cdot \delta u dV ds + \int_I \int_{\Omega} (\partial_t u - v) \cdot \delta v dV dt \\ = \int_{\Omega} f \cdot \delta u dV + \int_{\partial \Omega_{N,u}} g_N \cdot \delta u dA dt + \int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho v^* \cdot \delta u dV ds. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Indeed according to the Proposition 2.2.14 we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_I \left(\int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \epsilon} : \delta \epsilon dV - \int_{\Omega} f \cdot \delta u dV - \int_{\partial \Omega_{N,u}} g_N \cdot \delta u dA \right) dt - \int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u} \cdot \delta u dV dt \\ - \int_I \int_{\partial \Omega_{D,u}} c_u (u - g_D) \cdot \delta u dA dt + \int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u}^* \cdot \delta u dV ds = 0 \quad \forall \delta u. \end{aligned}$$

But we also recall that by integration by parts we have:

$$\begin{aligned} - \int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u} \cdot \delta u dV dt + \int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{u}^* \cdot \delta u dV ds &= - \int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho (\dot{u} - \dot{u}^*) \cdot \delta u dV ds + \int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho \ddot{u} \cdot \delta u dV dt \\ &= - \int_{\Omega} \rho (\dot{u} - \dot{u}^*) \cdot \delta u dV |_{t=T} - \int_{\Omega} \rho (\dot{u} - \dot{u}^*) \cdot \delta u dV |_{t=0} \\ &\quad + \int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho \ddot{u} \cdot \delta u dV dt. \end{aligned}$$

So, by replacing this equality in the last one we get the equation and also knowing that $\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \epsilon} = \sigma$ and $\epsilon = \nabla^{sym} u := \nabla u$, we have that:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_I \left(\int_{\Omega} \sigma : \nabla \delta u dV - \int_{\Omega} f \cdot \delta u dV - \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,u}} g_N \cdot \delta u dA \right) dt + \int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{v} \cdot \delta u dV dt \\ & - \int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho v \cdot \delta u dV dt - \int_I \int_{\partial\Omega_{D,u}} c_u (u - g_D) \cdot \delta u dA dt + \int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho v^* \cdot \delta u dV ds = 0 \quad \forall \delta u. \end{aligned}$$

But since δu here is taken in \mathcal{H}_0^u as seen in the previous part, we have the test function displacement which vanishes in the boundary Dirichlet of Ω so in fact the term $\int_I \int_{\partial\Omega_{D,u}} c_u (u - g_D) \cdot \delta u dA dt$ is vanished and then we obtain $\forall \delta u \in \mathcal{H}_0^u$ and $\forall \delta v \in \mathcal{H}^v$:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_I \left(\int_{\Omega} \sigma : \nabla \delta u dV - \int_{\Omega} f \cdot \delta u dV - \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,u}} g_N \cdot \delta u dA \right) dt + \int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{v} \cdot \delta u dV dt \\ & - \int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho v \cdot \delta u dV dt + \int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho v^* \cdot \delta u dV ds = 0. \end{aligned}$$

And now let us not forget the equation $\dot{u} = v$ which is weakly formulated as:

$$\int_I \int_{\Omega} (\dot{u} - v) \cdot \delta v dV dt = 0.$$

Then, by addition of the two last equations we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_I \int_{\Omega} \sigma : \nabla \delta u dV + \int_I \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{v} \cdot \delta u dV dt - \int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho v \cdot \delta u dV ds + \int_I \int_{\Omega} (\partial_t u - v) \cdot \delta v dV dt \\ & = \int_I \int_{\Omega} f \cdot \delta u dV + \int_I \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,u}} g_N \cdot \delta u dA dt + \int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho v^* \cdot \delta u dV ds. \end{aligned}$$

□

3.3.4 Remark. As recall the term $\int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho v^* \cdot \delta u dV ds$ contains the time velocity conditions in initial time $t = 0$ and final time $t = T$ imposed weakly into the system via this term as seen in chapter 2.

3.3.5 Continous Galerkin Discretization. Again here we are going to use the same idea to discretize our unusual system. Indeed, we are going to define first in space the discrete finite dimensional space, the discretize in time using the continuous Galerkin method to write the fully discrete variational system.

So, as done in the previous section, we are going to keep our set W^h as defined in 3.2.5.

As previously done for the temporal discretization of the classical case we consider our interval I decomposed in M subintervals, such that $I = \cup_{m=1}^M$, and where:

$$I_m = [t_{m-1}, t_m], \quad k_m = t_m - t_{m-1}, \quad k := \max_{m \in \{1, \dots, M\}} k_m.$$

Having from the previous part, the weak formulation of our unusual system in Proposition 3.3.3 can still be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{m=1}^M \int_{I_m} \int_{\Omega} \sigma : \nabla \delta u dV + \sum_{m=1}^M \int_{I_m} \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{v} \cdot \delta u dV dt - \int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho v \cdot \delta u dV ds = \sum_{m=1}^M \int_{I_m} \int_{\Omega} f \cdot \delta u dV \\ & + \sum_{m=1}^M \int_{I_m} \int_{\partial\Omega_{N,u}} g_N \cdot \delta u dA dt + \int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho v^* \cdot \delta u dV ds, \end{aligned}$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^M \int_{I_m} \int_{\Omega} (\partial_t u - v) \cdot \delta v \, dV dt = 0.$$

We keep our trial functions and test functions spaces defined for the temporal discretization which are our temporal finite element spaces $W_{h,k}^c$ and $W_{h,k}^d$ as defined in equations 3.2.6 - 3.2.7 respectively and then we can write our fully discrete variational problem for this case as:

$\forall (\delta u, \delta v) \in W_{h,k}^d \times W_{h,k}^d$ we seek to find the couple solution $(u, v) \in W_{h,k}^c \times W_{h,k}^c$ such that:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{m=1}^M \int_{I_m} \int_{\Omega} \sigma : \nabla \delta u \, dV + \sum_{m=1}^M \int_{I_m} \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{v} \cdot \delta u \, dV dt - \int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho v \cdot \delta u \, dV ds = \sum_{m=1}^M \int_{I_m} \int_{\Omega} f \cdot \delta u \, dV \\ + \sum_{m=1}^M \int_{I_m} \int_{\partial \Omega_{N,u}} g_N \cdot \delta u \, dA dt + \int_{\partial I} \int_{\Omega} \rho v^* \cdot \delta u \, dV ds, \end{aligned}$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^M \int_{I_m} \int_{\Omega} (\partial_t u - v) \cdot \delta v \, dV dt = 0.$$

(3.3.1)

4. Analysis and Simulations: Results and Discussions

Numerical simulations for the uncommon wave equation, which has starting and final time velocity conditions, as well as the classical wave equation which has initial displacement and velocity conditions are discussed in this chapter. The main goal is to clarify the effect of final time velocity condition on the solution by analyzing the error behavior of the uncommon situation and where appropriate, comparing it to the classical example. In order to do this, we use the FeniCS library in python to implement the space-time continuous Galerkin finite element method, according to its code repositories and documentation which can be found in [1]. We will consider two types of dataset, one with a null body force term f and the other one with a non null term f . By proceeding to some variations on the mesh refinements as well as on the approximate polynomial degrees, we aim to provide insights into the numerical performance and accuracy of our unusual wave equation.

4.1 Numerical setup

4.1.1 Description of the datasets. For our analysis, we work with the spatial domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}$ and we assume the function $g_N = 0$. We detail the datasets that we use for the implementations, as first datasets we have:

- $\Omega = [0, 1], I = [0, 4]$,
- The body force $f(x, t) = (2 - x(1 - x))\sin(t)$,
- The exact solution that we use is $u(x, t) = \sin(t)x(1 - x), v(x, t) = \cos(t)x(1 - x)$,
- We have boundary conditions as well as initial ones which are: $u(x, 0) = 0, v(x, 0) = x(1 - x), v(x, 4) = \cos(4)x(1 - x), u(0, t) = u(1, t) = 0$.

Also we will use as second datasets for the implementations for the both cases(classical case as well as the unusual case):

- $\Omega = [0, 1], I = [0, 4]$,
- The body force $f(x, t) = 0$,
- The exact solution that we use is $u(x, t) = \sin(\pi t)\sin(\pi x), v(x, t) = \pi\cos(\pi t)\sin(\pi x)$,
- We have boundary conditions as well as initial ones which are: $u(x, 0) = 0, v(x, 0) = \pi\sin(\pi x), v(x, 4) = \pi\sin(\pi x), u(0, t) = u(1, t) = 0$.

4.1.2 Briefly description of the numerical method. We give some descriptions of our numerical method.

Our numerical code is based on the space-time continuous Galerkin finite element method implemented using the library FeniCS. We first define a mixed function space for displacement u and velocity v using

the Lagrange element polynomial (of degree 1 and 2). Then, we set the variational problem and we study the L^2 error which is the norm $\|U - U_h\|_{L^2}$ where $U = (u, v)$ and $U_h = (u_h, v_h)$ following different refinement strategies of the spatial (N_x) and temporal mesh (N_t) which are the cases:

- Same space-time refinement, $(N_x, N_t) = (50, 50), (100, 100), (200, 200), (400, 400)$
- Refinement in Space only $(N_x, N_t) = (100, 50), (200, 50), (400, 50), (800, 50), (1600, 50), (3200, 50), (6400, 50)$.
- Refinement only in time $(N_x, N_t) = (50, 100), (50, 200), (50, 400), (50, 800), (50, 1600), (50, 3200), (50, 6400)$.

4.2 Simulation results

In this part we give all the tables containing the errors that we have got after our simulations including all the different cases in two different types, the first type concern the first datasets in the classical and the unusual case and the second one is related to the second datasets as describe in the previous subsection in the both problem cases again.

4.2.1 Simulations related to the first dataset. Here, for the first dataset, results for both the classical problem and the unusual problem are presented in two different scenarios.

- **Classical problem:** As first result of simulations, here we will give the one from the classical case with the polynomials approximating the solution u, v all of them of Lagrange and of degree at most 1. Considering the Lagrange of degree 1 approximation for both u and v , the results of L^2 error for corresponding space-time refinement, space refinement, and time refinement are given in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: L^2 errors for the classical problem with linear approximation for u and linear for v

Space-time refinement		Space refinement ($N_t = 50$)		Time refinement ($N_x = 50$)	
(N_x, N_t)	L^2 error	N_x	L^2 error	N_t	L^2 error
(50,50)	3.7018×10^{-3}	(100,50)	2.0501×10^{-3}	(50,100)	1.1015×10^{-3}
(100,100)	7.4361×10^{-4}	(200,50)	1.9225×10^{-3}	(50,200)	2.0681×10^{-3}
(200,200)	2.2195×10^{-4}	(400,50)	1.9123×10^{-3}	(50,400)	2.8768×10^{-1}
(400,400)	6.6875×10^{-5}	(800,50)	1.9110×10^{-3}	(50,800)	2.6935×10^{-1}
				(50,1600)	3.4843×10^{-1}
				(50,3200)	3.1015×10^{-1}
				(50,6400)	1.7483×10^{-1}

We also conducted numerical approximation for the classical case, considering quadratic approximation for u and linear approximation for v . The L^2 error for this case is presented in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2: L^2 errors for the classical problem with quadratic approximation for u and linear for v

Space-time refinement		Space refinement ($N_t = 50$)		Time refinement ($N_x = 50$)	
(N_x, N_t)	L^2 error	N_x	L^2 error	N_t	L^2 error
(50,50)	1.1152×10^{-1}	(100,50)	2.0785×10^{-1}	(50,100)	9.7275×10^{-2}
(100,100)	1.1253×10^{-1}	(200,50)	4.1190×10^{-1}	(50,200)	5.1475×10^{-2}
(200,200)	1.7008×10^{-1}	(400,50)	8.3319×10^{-1}	(50,400)	1.5971×10^{-2}
(400,400)	5.1814×10^{-2}	(800,50)	$1.9955 \times 10^{+0}$	(50,800)	1.6057×10^{-1}
				(50,1600)	9.9737×10^{-3}
				(50,3200)	1.0675×10^{-2}

- **Unusual problem:** Still with the first dataset, we have some results on the unusual problem with initial and final time conditions considering polynomial approximation of order at most 1 for both u and v over the element space-time mesh. Here, we present as done in the previous part for the classical case, the different error approximations, following the space time refinements in time and space, see Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: L^2 errors for the unusual problem with linear approximation for u and linear for v

Space-time refinement		Space refinement ($N_t = 50$)		Time refinement ($N_x = 50$)	
(N_x, N_t)	L^2 error	N_x	L^2 error	N_t	L^2 error
(50,50)	7.7302×10^{-2}	(100,50)	7.8989×10^{-2}	(50,100)	7.1580×10^{-2}
(100,100)	7.7526×10^{-2}	(200,50)	7.9097×10^{-2}	(50,200)	5.5610×10^{-2}
(200,200)	7.7180×10^{-2}	(400,50)	7.9198×10^{-2}	(50,400)	3.1813×10^{-2}
(400,400)	7.7138×10^{-2}	(800,50)	7.9225×10^{-2}	(50,800)	1.5980×10^{-2}
				(50,1600)	1.0221×10^{-2}
				(50,3200)	8.6135×10^{-3}
				(50,6400)	8.1999×10^{-3}

For this unusual case, we also conducted simulation assuming that the polynomials approximating the solution u is of order at most 2 and linear for v . These results are shown below in Table 4.4 for different refinement cases.

Table 4.4: L^2 errors for the unusual problem with quadratic approximation for u and linear for v

Space-time refinement		Space refinement ($N_t = 50$)		Time refinement ($N_x = 50$)	
(N_x, N_t)	L^2 error	N_x	L^2 error	N_t	L^2 error
(50, 50)	$1.6236 \times 10^{+0}$	100	4.9955×10^{-1}	100	$1.1911 \times 10^{+1}$
(100, 100)	$5.7368 \times 10^{+0}$	200	1.3817×10^{-1}	200	$4.4351 \times 10^{+1}$
(200, 200)	1.9012×10^1	400	4.1183×10^{-2}	400	$1.1919 \times 10^{+2}$
(400, 400)	5.8788×10^1	800	1.6486×10^{-2}	800	$2.6444 \times 10^{+2}$
		1600	1.0282×10^{-2}	1600	$5.1401 \times 10^{+2}$
		3200	8.7281×10^{-3}	3200	$7.6315 \times 10^{+2}$
		6400	8.3291×10^{-3}	6400	$1.0484 \times 10^{+3}$

4.2.2 Simulations related to the second datasets.

- **Classical problem:** Here we consider the case where we recall our body force f is null, and our approximating polynomials for both solution u and v are of degree 1, so we get these tables resuming the L^2 error approximation following the different refinement cases which are given in Table 4.5.

Table 4.5: L^2 errors for the classical problem with linear approximation for u and linear for v

Space-time refinement		Space refinement ($N_t = 50$)		Time refinement ($N_x = 50$)	
(N_x, N_t)	L^2 error	N_x	L^2 error	N_t	L^2 error
(50,50)	1.6537×10^{-1}	100	1.5552×10^{-1}	100	3.7727×10^{-2}
(100,100)	3.8460×10^{-2}	200	1.5530×10^{-1}	200	6.0728×10^{-2}
(200,200)	9.6853×10^{-3}	400	1.5529×10^{-1}	400	$5.7996 \times 10^{+0}$
(400,400)	2.4833×10^{-3}	800	1.5530×10^{-1}	800	$5.5347 \times 10^{+0}$
				1600	$5.7248 \times 10^{+0}$
				3200	$5.2219 \times 10^{+0}$
				6400	$3.3072 \times 10^{+0}$

We consider now a quadratic approximation for the solution u and a linear approximation for the solution v , and conduct numerical results with the same dataset 2 the results from the simulations are given in Table 4.6.

Table 4.6: L^2 errors for the classical problem with quadratic approximation for the discrete solution u and a linear approximation for the discrete solution v

Space-time refinement		Space refinement ($N_t = 50$)		Time refinement ($N_x = 50$)	
(N_x, N_t)	L^2 error	N_x	L^2 error	N_t	L^2 error
(50,50)	$1.4463 \times 10^{+1}$	100	$3.2670 \times 10^{+1}$	100	$1.0137 \times 10^{+1}$
(100,100)	$1.3816 \times 10^{+1}$	200	$7.2167 \times 10^{+1}$	200	$3.5467 \times 10^{+0}$
(200,200)	$3.0965 \times 10^{+1}$	400	$1.5478 \times 10^{+2}$	400	$1.1450 \times 10^{+0}$
(400,400)	$7.6830 \times 10^{+0}$	800	$3.8398 \times 10^{+2}$	800	$6.3839 \times 10^{+0}$
		1600	$9.9271 \times 10^{+2}$	1600	3.1088×10^{-1}
		3200	$1.9212 \times 10^{+3}$	3200	1.3992×10^{-1}

- **Unusual problem:** Now, we consider our unusual problem case and we assume that the discrete solution of u and v are approximated by polynomials of degree 1 and we have the following results from the conducted simulations for the L^2 error in Table 4.7.

Table 4.7: L^2 errors for the unusual problem with linear approximation for u and linear for v

Space-time refinement		Space refinement ($N_t = 50$)		Time refinement ($N_x = 50$)	
(N_x, N_t)	L^2 error	N_x	L^2 error	N_t	L^2 error
(50,50)	8.6635×10^{-2}	100	8.5961×10^{-2}	100	7.4393×10^{-2}
(100,100)	2.0981×10^{-2}	200	8.5512×10^{-2}	200	4.2088×10^{-2}
(200,200)	5.2072×10^{-3}	400	8.5476×10^{-2}	400	6.4414×10^{-3}
(400,400)	1.2965×10^{-3}	800	8.5469×10^{-2}	800	2.5798×10^{-3}
		1600	8.5468×10^{-2}	1600	2.2513×10^{-3}
		3200	8.5467×10^{-2}	3200	2.2124×10^{-3}
		6400	8.5467×10^{-2}	6400	2.2030×10^{-3}

We still consider our unusual problem case and we assume that the solution of u is approximated by quadratic polynomials and the solution of v is approximated by linear polynomials, by conducting simulation we have the following results in Table 4.8.

Table 4.8: L^2 errors for the unusual problem with quadratic approximation for u and linear for v

Space-time refinement		Space refinement ($N_t = 50$)		Time refinement ($N_x = 50$)	
(N_x, N_t)	L^2 error	N_x	L^2 error	N_t	L^2 error
(50,50)	8.0690×10^{-1}	100	5.7071×10^{-1}	100	$1.1615 \times 10^{+0}$
(100,100)	$1.3994 \times 10^{+0}$	200	3.1877×10^{-1}	200	9.1392×10^{-1}
(200,200)	$2.2242 \times 10^{+0}$	400	1.6459×10^{-1}	400	5.4738×10^{-1}
(400,400)	$3.1573 \times 10^{+0}$	800	8.3764×10^{-2}	800	2.9286×10^{-1}
		1600	4.3623×10^{-2}	1600	1.4444×10^{-1}
		3200	2.4871×10^{-2}	3200	6.6250×10^{-2}
		6400	1.7236×10^{-2}	6400	2.7781×10^{-2}

4.3 Analysis and insights

In order to compare the atypical wave equation with an extra final time velocity condition to the classical wave equation with starting displacement and velocity conditions, we focus on the numerical simulation results shown in Tables 4.1–4.8. The L^2 error behavior, the influence of the final velocity condition, polynomial degree effects, dataset differences, and the relative contribution of time versus space refinement are the main topics of the investigation. With linear (degree 1) and quadratic (degree 2) Lagrange elements for the displacement u and velocity v in a mixed function space, the simulations were carried out using the continuous Galerkin finite element (cG-FEM) implemented in FEniCS with our two datasets defined above.

4.3.1 Error Behavior for Different Datasets. Here, we give some analysis on the error behavior depending of the dataset. First of all, we consider the dataset 1 and discussed the error of the classical problem and unusual problem with linear approximation below.

The classical case with linear elements is presented in Table 4.1. This exhibits significant error reduction under space-time refinement, with L^2 errors decreasing from 3.7018×10^{-3} ($N_x = N_t = 50$) to 6.6875×10^{-5} ($N_x = N_t = 400$). Speaking about the convergence order, we compute the ratio of errors of consecutive mesh size usually from a mesh size and its double, if in average it is around

3.5-5.5 (e.g., here we have $\frac{3.7018 \times 10^{-3}}{7.4361 \times 10^{-4}} \approx 4.98$) which is the error reduction's factor, it is suggesting a quadratic convergence so a convergence of order 2. We recall that for defining the order of convergence p of a numerical scheme in general, we can take two errors from successive mesh size $N = 50, E_1$ and $N_2 = 100, E_2$ and we have: $p \approx \frac{\log(\frac{E_1}{E_2})}{\log(\frac{N_2}{N_1})}$ for example in our case above $p \approx 2, 3$ that is why we said to be close to the quadratic convergence. However, space-only refinement shows minimal error reduction (from 2.0501×10^{-3}) to 1.9110×10^{-3} , suggesting that accuracy is limited by the temporal discretization. Moreover, time only refinement shows erratic behavior with error increasing significantly from $N_t \geq 400, 2.8768 \times 10^{-1}$, likely due to the lack of spatial resolution.

The Unusual case with linear elements is given in Table 4.3. The practically constant errors (around 7.7×10^{-2}) obtained via space time-refinement point to a lack of convergence, which might be caused by the global influence of the condition of ending time velocity $v(x, 4) = \cos(4)x(1 - x)$. Temporal resolution is crucial for capturing the final time condition, as evidenced by the slight increase in errors from space-only refinement to 7.9225×10^{-2} and the significant reduction from 7.1580×10^{-2} to 8.1999×10^{-3} from time-only refinement.

Secondly, we considered the dataset 2 and discussed the approximation error on the classical case and unusual case with linear approximation polynomial. This finding are presented as in the following.

The classical case with linear elements is given in Table 4.5. It presents a strong convergence under space-time refinement here, with errors dropping from 1.6537×10^{-1} to 2.4833×10^{-3} . This results in a error reduction's factor of roughly 4 (e.g., $\frac{1.6537 \times 10^{-1}}{3.8460 \times 10^{-2}} \approx 4.30$, which again suggests a quadratic convergence as properties. Time-only refinement leads to increasing errors for $N_t \geq 400$, reaching 5.7996×10^0 indicating a certain numerical instability, whereas space-only refinement shows stagnant errors(around 1.55×10^{-1}).

The unusual case is presented in Table 4.7. This shows better convergence over space-time refinement (from 8.6635×10^{-2} to 1.2965×10^{-3} , factor of the error reduction ≈ 4) and time-only refinement reduces error to 2.2030×10^{-3} whereas space-only refinement produces nearly constant errors(around 8.54×10^{-2}).

By comparing simulation results over polynomial degrees, we notice that:

- Quadratic element for u (with linear for v) in the classical case (Tables 4.2 & 4.6) generally produce higher order errors than the linear case, especially in dataset 2 (e.g., 1.4463×10^1 , Table 4.6 vs. 1.6537×10^{-1} with approximation of u and v , Table 4.5 at $N_x = N_t = 50$).
- For the unusual case (Tables 4.4 & 4.8), quadratic element for u leads to significantly larger errors (e.g., 5.8788×10^1 , Table 4.8 vs. 7.7138×10^{-2} , Table 4.7 for dataset 2, $N_x = N_t = 400$), suggesting that the final time condition amplifies the numerical challenges with high-order elements.

Trends: The classical case consistently shows better convergence over space-time refinement, while the unusual case often exhibits higher errors or slower convergence, particularly (higher) in dataset 1, likely due to the final time condition's global influence and at this stage, we assume maybe the potential influence of the term f . Time-only refinement is more effective in the unusual case, especially with linear elements, suggesting that temporal accuracy is critical for handling the final condition.

4.3.2 Impact of Final Velocity Condition. Our unusual wave equation incorporates a final time velocity condition $v(x, T) = v_T^*$, which imposes a constraint at the end time interval ($T = 4$ for both

datasets). This condition significantly affect error magnitudes and convergence rates. In dataset 1, the unusual case with linear element (Table 4.3) shows nearly constant error under space-time refinement ($\approx 7.7 \times 10^{-2}$) and space-only refinement. Unlike the classical case's steady decrease (Table 4.1, 3.7018×10^{-3} to 6.6875×10^{-5}). This suggest that the final time condition introduces a global constraint that limits the spatial convergence, as the solution must satisfy $v(x, 4) = \cos(4)x(1 - x)$, affecting the entire space-time cylinder.

Time-only refinement (Table 4.3) reduces errors significantly (to 8.1999×10^{-3}), indicating that final temporal meshes helps to capture the final condition accurately.

For the dataset 2, the unusual case (Table 4.7) shows better convergence over space-time refinement with (rate ≈ 4) compared to the dataset 1, possibly due to the zero body force ($f = 0$) which reduces numerical complexity. Moreover, errors in the unusual case become lower than those from the classical case whatever the polynomial approximation order of u (quadratic or linear) and for all types of refinement (e.g., space-time refinement 1.2965×10^{-3} , Table 4.7 vs. 2.4833×10^{-3} at $N_x = N_t = 400$, Table 4.5), suggesting again that the lack of the body force f is an important factor for allowing the unusual case to perform or even outperform the classical case in accuracy for this dataset.

The final condition introduces numerical challenges in the space-time cG-FEM, as the weak formulation includes boundary terms at $t = T$ (see Proposition 3.3.3), requiring the solution to align globally across time. This can lead to error accumulation, especially with coarser meshes in time, as the solver balances initial and final conditions of time simultaneously. However in dataset 2, the simply dynamics enable the final time condition to act as an additional constraint that refines the solution, with sufficient mesh refinement.

4.3.3 Polynomial Degree Effects. Using quadratic elements for u (with linear v) generally increases errors compare to the linear element for both cases, contrary to expectations, as higher-order element typically improve accuracy. For the classical case in dataset 1 (Table 4.2), space-time refinement yields higher errors (e.g., 1.1152×10^{-1} at $N_x = N_t = 50$) than linear elements (Table 4.1, 3.7018×10^{-3} at $N_x = N_t = 50$). In dataset 2 (Table 4.6), errors are even larger (e.g., 1.4463×10^1). For the unusual case, quadratic elements (Tables 4.4 & 4.8) produce significantly larger errors, especially in dataset 1 (e.g., 5.8788×10^1 , Table 4.4 at $N_x = N_t = 400$). This suggests that quadratic elements for u introduce numerical instability, possibly due to mismatched polynomial degrees between u and v so the linear approximation for v limits overall accuracy, as the velocity field may dominates the error contributions in the wave equation.

4.3.4 Dataset Comparison.

- **Dataset 1** ($f \neq 0$) features a non-zero body force $f(x, t) = (2 - x(1 - x)) \sin(t)$, a longer time interval ($I = [0, 4]$), and an exact solution $u(x, t) = \sin(t)x(1 - x)$. This complexity leads to smaller errors in the classical case with linear elements (e.g., in space-time refinement Table 4.1, 6.6875×10^{-5} , $N_x = N_t = 400$) but poor convergence in the unusual case (e.g., in space-time refinement Table 4.3, $\approx 7.7 \times 10^{-2}$, $N_x = N_t = 400$). So the non-zero body force introduces additional dynamics, increasing sensitivity to mesh refinement and polynomial degree.
- **Dataset 2** ($f = 0$) has a simpler sinusoidal solution ($u = \sin(\pi t) \sin(\pi x)$) and a longer time interval ($I = [0, 4]$), leading to better convergence in both cases. The classical case (Table 4.5) achieves errors as low as 2.4833×10^{-3} , and the unusual case (Table 4.7) reaches 1.2965×10^{-3} . The absence of the body force simplifies the dynamics, reducing numerical errors and allowing the final time condition to be capture more easily in the unusual case.

The non zero body force in dataset 1 may increase error magnitudes, particularly in the unusual case where the final time condition and the natural dynamic forcing interact to limit convergence. The dataset 2's simpler setup highlights the numerical method's ability to handle the final time condition more effectively when external forces are absent.

4.3.5 Time vs. Space Refinement. The results indicate that time refinement is more critical than space refinement for both cases, especially for the unusual case. In dataset 1, classical time-only refinement (Table 4.1) shows erratic behavior, with errors increasing for $N_t \geq 400$, suggesting that fixed spatial resolution ($N_x = 50$) limits accuracy. In contrast, for the unusual case (Table 4.3) benefits significantly from time refinement, reducing errors from 7.1580×10^{-2} to 8.1999×10^{-3} . In dataset 2, time refinement in the unusual case (Table 4.7) is highly effective (the error drops to 2.2030×10^{-3}), while the classical case (Table 4.5) shows instability.

Space-only refinement consistently yields stagnant or slightly increasing errors in both cases and datasets, indicating that temporal discretization dominates error contributions which may be due to the wave equation's time-dependent nature and the final time condition's global effect in the unusual case. Balanced space-time refinement is necessary for optimal convergence, but temporal accuracy is paramount for capturing the dynamics accurately.

4.4 Discussion

4.4.1 Key Findings. The previous part on the analysis of the numerical simulation in subsection 4.3 underscores the profound impact of the source term f (body force) and the critical role of time refinement in the error analysis of the classical and unusual wave equations using the continuous Galerkin element method (cG-FEM). In dataset 1, with a non-zero source term f , the classical wave equation exhibits robust convergence, while the unusual wave equation, constrained by the final time velocity condition $v(x, 4) = \cos(4)x(1-x)$, shows stagnant error (Table 4.3), indicating that the complex dynamics introduced by f hinder convergence. In contrast, dataset 2, with $f = 0$, allows the unusual case to achieve superior accuracy, reducing errors to 1.2965×10^{-3} compared to 2.4833×10^{-3} for the classical case (Table 4.5 & 4.7), suggesting that simpler dynamics enhance the final condition's stabilizing effect. Also, time-only refinement is particularly effective for the unusual case, slashing errors from 7.1580×10^{-2} to 8.199×10^{-3} in dataset 1 (Table 4.3) and to 2.2030×10^{-3} in dataset 2 (Table 4.7), revealing that high temporal resolution is essential to capture the global influence of the final velocity condition.

This provides an intuition that fine temporal meshes are crucial for mitigating error accumulation in non-standard temporal constraints.

Surprisingly, one other thing is that, higher order approximations, such as quadratic polynomials for displacement u (with linear v), yield significantly larger errors, reaching 5.8788×10^1 for the unusual case (Table 4.4) possibly due to a certain cG scheme's sensitivity to mismatched polynomial degrees or its inherent structure.

4.4.2 Limitations. This study faces several limitations that impact its generalizability. Foremost is the lack of a theoretical a priori error estimate for the unusual wave equation with final time velocity conditions, which complicates predicting convergence behavior or quantifying the initial condition's effect, unlike the classical wave equation, where established analyses exist [7]. A theoretical proof of that error for our unusual case could be inspired from that proof in [7], by a rigorous analysis. Additionally,

the numerical experiments reveal significant issues with high order polynomial approximation: quadratic approximations for displacement u (with linear for v) produce large errors (e.g., 5.8788×10^{-1} , Table 4.4), and also combinations like quadratic polynomials for both u and v , or quadratic v with linear u , are not even compiling when implemented in python, likely due to numerical instability from mismatched polynomial degrees or the cG scheme's formulation. Which may not adequately handle higher-order terms in time-dependent problems. The cG scheme itself then may be a limitation, as its continuous temporal discretization may exacerbate errors when higher-order elements are used, particularly for the unusual case's non-standard boundary conditions. Also it worth mentioning to say that computational constraints further restrict the analysis, with mesh refinement capped at $N_x = N_t = 400$ for space-time and $N_t = 6400$, especially for the unusual case where temporal accuracy is critical. These limitations underscore the need for both theoretical advancements and improved numerical strategies.

4.4.3 Future Work. Future research should prioritize developing a priori error estimates for our unusual wave equation, adapting frameworks from the classical case (see [7]) to quantify the final time velocity condition's impact and guide numerical improvements. To address the poor performance of higher order approximation and testing balanced polynomial degrees as cubic or even quartic elements for both u and v , which leads to numerical instability, the use of alternative schemes like discontinuous Galerkin methods, which may better handle the cG scheme's limitations with non standard conditions as done in ([9]) where the advantage of using discontinuous Galerkin method in space-time has been shown for second order hyperbolic problems. Implementing adaptive mesh refinement, which dynamically adjust spatial and temporal meshes based on error indicator as done in [3] for a Galerkin discretization of the classical linear wave equation, could also enhance efficiency and accuracy, particularly for the unusual case.

Conclusion

This thesis provides important insights into the numerical behavior of the classical and unusual wave equations by demonstrating the effectiveness and difficulties of using the continuous Galerkin method to solve them. While the atypical wave equation, which was limited by a final time condition, demonstrated the crucial importance of time-only refinement and the influence of the source term on error stagnation when non-zero, the classical wave equation showed strong convergence. However, the unexpectedly low displacement performance of quadratic approximations highlights numerical instability issues that may be related to the design of the cG scheme. These discoveries enhance our knowledge of space-time finite element techniques and demonstrate their potential for use in applications related to mechanics and thermodynamics.

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